

Research Article

Woodball Scorecard Marking Mobile Application

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Abstract: *The increasing demand for real-time mobile applications in sports judging has led to the creation of a mobile app for woodball enthusiasts that leverages Internet of Things (IoT) technology. This project addresses issues such as biased judging, false scoring, and manual scorekeeping in woodball matches. The Woodball Scorecard Marking application, developed using Flutter, MySQL, and Arduino IDE, focuses on an interactive user interface that effectively presents data while ensuring information density. To validate its functionality and usability, the app underwent rigorous testing. Functional testing confirmed that the app's outcomes met expectations, while usability testing gathered feedback from both experts and actual users, who expressed satisfaction with its design and performance. This innovation modernizes woodball judging, enhances gameplay, and promotes fair competition by reducing bias and minimizing reliance on manual scorekeeping. The application equips referees with real-time data for quick, accurate decision-making on scoring validity, addressing situations like out-of-bound incidents and player actions. Additionally, the mobile application provides real-time updates that improve the experience for players and spectators, fostering greater engagement with the game. By automating score updates triggered by ball movements and reducing marking errors, this project introduces a more efficient and precise approach to woodball. Ultimately, it promotes sustainability in sports technology, positioning woodball at the forefront of innovation within the sports domain.*

Keywords: IOT; Scorecard; Woodball; false scoring

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1. INTRODUCTION

Woodball is a sport that originated in Taiwan and is now played in many countries around the world (Wood, 2016). It was a combination of golf and croquet and was played with a mallet and a wooden ball on a course that looks like a miniature golf course. The game's objective was to hit the wooden ball through a series of obstacles and into a target area using the least number of strokes possible. While woodball was getting popular around the world, the potential for biases in making judgments in the tournament still occurred, even though the game seemed fair to others who did not notice it (Lyngstad et al., 2020). Additionally, existing manual labour also needs to be eliminated so that other tasks can be completed quickly and efficiently (Leong, 2018). Hence, Woodball Scorecard Marking mobile application was developed to address the problems. The application was developed using Flutter framework, MySQL for database and ArduinoIDE for the sensors' programming. The score will be collected by microprocessor esp8266 and store the data in MySQL databases. The scores then were extracted to display in mobile application. Three user interface design principles were applied in the mobile application which were designing and presenting data, interactivity and information density.

2. METHODOLOGY

The Waterfall Model is an organized and sequential research process used to create a Woodball Scorecard Marking application for woodball enthusiasts. It is divided into five phases, which are requirement analysis, design, development, testing, and documentation. Requirement analysis is gathered through resources such as articles and journals. Requirement Analysis, the researcher identified problem statements and defined project objectives, scope, and significance. In Design phases of user interface system design (organizing and presenting data, interactivity and information density as shown in Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3), Entity-Relationship Diagram (ERD), Experimental Design, Flowchart, Context Diagram, and Sitemap were outlined. In Development phase, Woodball Scorecard Marking mobile application was developed with Flutter connected to MySQL serving as the database for storing scores that collected from scorecard marking system implemented with IoT. Testing involved evaluation by experts and users through Usability Testing (UT) and by the developer through Functionality Testing (FT). Finally, the Documentation phase involved gathering and documenting all relevant project information and activities.

Figure 1: Woodball Scorecard application Home interface

Figure 2: Woodball Scorecard score display interface

Figure 3: Woodball Scorecard History score legibility

3. FINDINGS

Two evaluations have been performed on the application to evaluate the system which were usability and functioning of Woodball Scorecard Marking application. 37 respondents including experts, sport students and actual users were involved in usability testing to evaluate the organizing and presenting data, interactivity and information density in the application. Furthermore, functional tests are carried out by the developers to evaluate the Woodball Scorecard Marking application to determine all test cases compute as expected. Significant number of users validated the application's user-centric design, receiving overwhelmingly positive feedback on score comprehension, accuracy, ease of navigation, absence of errors, and legibility of scoring history as shown in Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6.

Figure 4: Organizing and Presenting Data Results

Figure 5: Interactivity Results

Figure 6: Information Density Results

4. DISCUSSION

The integration of IoT technology into woodball's scorecard marking mobile applications represents a revolutionary advancement with far-reaching implications for the sport. This innovation empowers referees with real-time data, enabling swift and precise decision-making regarding scoring validity, from out-of-bound incidents to player actions, thereby enhancing fairness during gameplay. Moreover, the real-time updates provided by mobile applications elevate the overall experience for both players and spectators, fostering heightened engagement and a deeper connection with the game's progress.

5. CONCLUSION

Finally, the development of a Woodball Scorecard Marking mobile application greatly supports the effectiveness and acceptance of the application integrated with IoT. The project not only met its objectives but also garnered positive feedback from experts and users alike, signifying its potential for enhancing woodball gameplay and fair competition. Based on performance result shows that Woodball Scorecard Marking application can be one of the solutions in preventing cheating and biased in woodball matches and reducing papers to save the environment. Thus, the project also greatly helps in reducing papers for scorecard marking.

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